

$$\text{with } \beta_L = \left[\frac{[\text{H}^+]^4}{k_1 k_2 k_3 k_4} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^3}{k_2 k_3 k_4} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_3 k_4} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_4} + 1 \right]^{-1} \quad \dots (9)$$

The values of acid dissociation constants k_1 , k_2 , etc., were obtained from a handbook⁴.

However, the expression for the formation constant will be

$$K_{\text{VO}_2\text{L}} = \frac{K_{\text{VO}_2\text{HL}} \cdot K_{\text{VO}_2\text{HL}}}{k_4} \quad \dots (10)$$

The obtained values are compared with corresponding values of EDTA complexes^{1,2}. It transpires that the species $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EDTA})^{-2}$ ($pK_a = 3.60$) is more acidic than $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EGTA})^{-2}$ ($pK_a = 5.49$) whereas the stability values of the species $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EDTA})^{-2}$ (11.39) and $\text{VO}_2(\text{EDTA})^{-3}$ (18.05) are more than the corresponding $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EGTA})^{-2}$ (7.73) and $\text{VO}_2(\text{EGTA})^{-3}$ (11.18). This may be attributed to the steric effect due to longer linking chain between the two nitrogen atoms separating the carboxylic acid groups apart in the EGTA molecule as compared to the shorter separation in EDTA. The plateau region of the $\text{VO}_2^+-\text{EGTA}$ system (Fig. 1) is shorter than that of $\text{VO}_2^+-\text{EDTA}$ system¹ which may be due to the same reason.

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Estimation of Thiourea, Allyl Thiourea and Toly Thiourea by Sodium N-Chloro- ρ -Toluene Sulphonamide†

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THE mechanism of oxidation of thioureas has been the subject of many investigations¹. Thiourea and its derivatives are generally oxidised to the corresponding disulphide², although instances of oxidation beyond the disulphide stage are also known³. Several oxidising agents have been used for assaying these compounds⁴⁻⁹ and an excellent

review of the subject by Balwanth Singh *et al*¹⁰ is noteworthy. Thioureas find a number of industrial applications in rubber vulcanization, electrodeposition of metals, corrosion inhibition, photography and in polymer, textile and agricultural industries. Sodium N-chloro- ρ -toluene sulphonamide (Chloramine-T), has been used in estimations of thiourea and its derivatives in slightly concentrated sulphuric acid and at high temperatures¹¹. However, this method is less accurate because of the decomposition of chloramine-T at high temperatures¹². The present communication deals with the estimation of thiourea (TU), allyl thiourea (ATU) and toly thiourea (TTU) by chloramine-T under mild experimental conditions.

Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified¹³ and used. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Solutions were prepared using triple distilled water. Chloramine-T (CAT) solution was standardised by iodometric method.

Since the oxidation reactions are not instantaneous under the given experimental conditions and the optimum medium contains sufficient amount of HCl, direct visual titration and potentiometric titration were not carried out. Hence, back titration procedure was adopted for the estimations of these compounds.

In preliminary experiments with CAT, known amounts of TU, ATU and TTU prepared in the appropriate buffer¹⁴ or solvent were added to a known and excessive volume (10-20%) of CAT solution in iodine flasks at 30°. The reaction mixtures were set aside for various intervals of time, with occasional shaking. Then the excess of CAT was determined by back titration. A typical set of results for the extent of oxidation of TU, ATU and TTU in different media are given in Table 1. Oxidations of TU and ATU are not reproducible and

TABLE 1—EXTENT OF OXIDATION OF THIOUREA, ALLYL THIOUREA AND TOLYL THIOUREA IN DIFFERENT MEDIA WITH EXCESS OF CHLORAMINE-T AT 30°C

Medium	%Oxidation			Medium	%Oxidation		
	TU	ATU	TTU		TU	ATU	TTU
0.6M HCl	100.1	100.2	48.0	pH*2	77.4	91.1	94.4
0.5M HCl	99.2	100.1	49.6	pH†3	80.3	93.0	85.8
0.4M HCl	97.7	100.0	49.6	pH**4	84.5	93.6	70.5
0.3M HCl	96.5	97.0	50.4	pH**5	92.1	94.0	68.7
0.2M HCl	93.6	92.1	51.1	pH**6	95.0	96.0	65.6
pH*1	92.9	89.5	70.4	pH††7	96.5	98.0	63.0

[CAT] taken $5 \times 10^{-3}M$, [TU], [ATU] and [TTU] taken $7 \times 10^{-4}M$
 *HCl-KCl buffer, **Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer,
 †Potassiumbipthalate-HCl buffer. ††Borax-boric acid buffer.
 Time : 30 minutes for ATU and TTU, 45 minutes for TU.

non-stoichiometric in various media other than HCl solutions. The % oxidation increases gradually as the concentration of HCl increases, but the increase becomes rapid at or above 0.5N HCl. However,

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the oxidation reaction of TTU is stoichiometric and rapid in 8M CH₃COOH solution containing 0.5M HCl.

Recommended Procedure :

Prepare aqueous solutions of TU, ATU (0.01M). Add aliquots containing 0.1-2.5 mM to measured excessive (10-20%) volume of 0.01N CAT containing enough HCl to make the overall acid concentration (0.5-0.6M). In the case of TTU, add sufficient amounts of CH₃COOH and HCl to the medium to get the resulting concentrations 8M and 0.5M, respectively. Shake the mixtures and keep it in a thermostat at 30° for 30 min in the cases of TTU and ATU and 45 min for TU. Add 10 ml of 10% KI solution along with 10 ml of 2N H₂SO₄. Titrate the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate solution. Run a blank experiment with CAT under identical conditions without TU, ATU and TTU. Amounts (mgs) of TU, ATU and TTU in the sample solutions are given by the equation

$$X = Wy (V_1 - V_2)$$

where y is the normality of the thiosulphate solution, V₁ is the blank titre value and V₂ is the test titre value. W takes the values of 9.5, 9.71 and 13.88 for TU, ATU and TTU respectively. From the reaction products, sulphate and *p*-toluene sulfanamide are isolated and characterised. In the cases of ATU and TTU substituted amines are detected.

Some typical results of analysis of TU, ATU and TTU in aqueous solutions are given in Table 2. The

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF THIOUREA, ALLYL THIOUREA AND TOLYL THIOUREA BY CHLORAMINE-T AT 30°C

Thiourea*		Allyl Thiourea**		Tolyl Thiourea***	
taken (mg)	found (mg)	taken (mg)	found (mg)	taken (mg)	found (mg)
1.90	1.91	2.32	2.30	1.66	1.67
3.80	3.77	4.64	4.60	3.32	3.32
7.60	7.65	5.81	5.85	4.98	4.94
11.40	11.38	11.62	11.62	6.64	6.67
15.20	15.25	17.20	17.05	8.30	8.40
19.00	19.10	23.20	23.40	12.45	12.40
22.80	22.70	29.25	29.40	16.61	16.45
30.40	30.35	34.86	34.65	20.77	20.77
38.00	38.30	40.66	40.39	24.93	24.98
45.60	45.40	46.40	46.80	29.05	29.15
53.20	53.35	50.20	49.80	33.20	33.45
60.80	60.50	55.00	54.50	37.35	37.10

*0.6M HCl **0.5M HCl ***8M CH₃COOH+0.5M HCl
Time: 30 minutes for ATU and TTU, 45 minutes for TU.

values obtained are accurate within 1%. The detailed study of oxidation of TU, ATU and TTU by CAT has brought out the following facts :

(1) ATU and TTU undergo oxidation with 12 electron change, whereas TU is oxidised with 8 electron change.

(2) Foreign ions such as nitrate, perchlorate and sulphate ions have no influence (up to ionic strength 0.25)

(3) Chloride ion has slight effect on the rate of oxidation.

(4) The stoichiometry is unaffected by the reversal of the order of addition of oxidant and thioureas.

In acidic chloride solutions CAT gives several oxidising species^{1,5,16} such as RNCl₂, RNHCl, H₂OCl⁺ and Cl₂, which may oxidise these organic substrates. Kinetics of oxidation of TU, ATU and TTU is under detailed investigation which may throw light on the mechanism of oxidation by CAT.

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